

Kharkiv Food Security Forum

“KHARKIV ON THE WAY TO FOOD SECURITY: FOOD PRACTICES AND 5R PRINCIPLES”

07 December 2023

Kharkiv

Kharkiv Food Security Forum

“Kharkiv on the way to food security: food practices and 5R principles”

was held on December 07, 2023 at V. N. Karazin Kharkiv National University as part of the international research project Fusilli.

Olena Muradyan
Dean of the School of Sociology,
Karazin University; Fusilli
project manager in Ukraine.

“The main goal of the forum is to share experiences and discuss issues related to the transformation of Kharkiv's food systems in the context of war; volunteerism and humanitarian support for the de-occupied territories; social entrepreneurship and local food initiatives; responsible consumption and waste circulation; food practices and sustainable development goals; and prospects for food policy in the city and region.”

In this brochure, we would like to tell you about the activities of the forum participants and highlight the main points of their reports, as the invited stakeholders are actively working on food security issues in Kharkiv and Kharkiv region during the war. Among the invited participants of our forum were:

- Kharkiv City Council;
- Department of Agricultural Development of the Kharkiv Regional Military Administration;
- The Main Department of the State Service of Ukraine for Food Safety and Consumer Protection in Kharkiv region;
- Charitable organization “Charitable Foundation “Source of the Revival” (CFSR);
- Relief Coordination Center (Kharkiv Region);
- FSLC in Kharkiv Region;
- Humanitarian organization “Corus International”;
- “Zero Waste Kharkiv”;
- NGO “Green Landia”;
- Karazin Institute of Environmental Sciences;
- School of Sociology, Karazin University.

Fusilli is an international research project that was won by a team from the School of Sociology at Karazin University back in 2020. It is an exciting project based on the development of urban nutrition plans in their local contexts to achieve an integrated, safe and holistic transition to healthy, sustainable, safe, inclusive and cost-effective food systems. The FUSILLI project is being implemented by twelve participating cities in Europe, and more than 30 participating organizations have joined the project consortium (<https://fusilli-project.eu/>)

The project received funding under the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No. 101000717.

Svitlana Gorbunova-Ruban

Deputy Mayor of Kharkiv for Healthcare and Social protection of the population

“Today, 35-36 thousand hot meals are distributed daily in Kharkiv for people who need this food. People are satisfied, and the queues are not decreasing. And so far, this service remains relevant.”

from an interview on 16 October 2023 for the Infocity Kharkiv news service

Since the beginning of the full-scale invasion, one of the key tasks of the Kharkiv City Council has been to maintain and ensure food security for the city's residents. This is especially true for vulnerable categories of the population and citizens living in the most heavily shelled areas of the city. Since the beginning of the invasion, social workers have been delivering hot meals to those categories of people who were staying at home alone and unable to go out to buy food (the elderly and people with disabilities). The city council also distributed food packages and organized and continues to organize events to support the food security of the city's residents.

Distribution of lunches for residents of Nemyshlyansky district. December 09, 2022 (photo by Suspilne Kharkiv)

Andriy Dorozhko

Director of the Department of Agricultural Development of the Kharkiv Regional Military Administration

“Food security is a key topic today, because we all know how much the agricultural sector of Kharkiv and the region has suffered due to the aggression of the Russian Federation. More than 630 enterprises in the region have been either destroyed or damaged by the occupation and hostilities. More than 1000 units of agricultural machinery were destroyed. According to preliminary estimates, the losses of the agricultural sector in the region amount to approximately UAH 18 billion. And this figure is only preliminary.”

The Department of Agricultural Development is responsible for assisting in the demining of agricultural land in the region, as well as coordinating the provision of humanitarian aid and financial assistance to farmers. In particular, it monitors requests from farmers and has created effective interaction platforms.

Agrarians of the region receive state support (photo by Department of Agricultural Development)

Svitlana Manets

Acting Head of the Main Directorate of the State Service of Ukraine for Food Safety and Consumer Protection in Kharkiv Region

Activities of the Main Directorate of the State Service of Ukraine for Food Safety and Consumer Protection in Kharkiv region

Areas of activity:

- Veterinary medicine and food safety: the department constantly monitors the state of livestock and food production, ensuring compliance with high safety and quality standards.
- Internal audit: a systematic analysis of internal processes and procedures to identify and correct possible risks in product quality.
- Supervision (control) in the system of engineering and technical support of the agro-industrial complex: ensuring a high technical level of production and verifying compliance of technological processes with norms and standards.
- State supervision over compliance with sanitary legislation: constant monitoring of the conditions of production, storage and transportation of food products in compliance with sanitary requirements.
- State price regulation: control over pricing policy in the food market to prevent manipulation and maintain market equilibrium.
- State supervision (control): conducting systematic inspections of compliance with food quality and safety standards.
- Phytosanitary safety: ensuring the safety of plant life and preventing the spread of plant pests and diseases.
- Consumer protection: ensuring the rights of consumers to quality and safe food products, providing the necessary information on the composition and nutritional properties of products.

Quality control of food and plant products: functions of the Main Directorate of the State Service of Ukraine for Food Safety and Consumer Protection in Kharkiv region

“The Main Directorate of the State Service of Ukraine for Food Safety and Consumer Protection in Kharkiv Region plays a key role in ensuring quality control of food and plant products, which is important for the health and safety of the region's residents.”

A management task that is particularly important during the war is to monitor compliance with sanitary standards for food production and preservation. The war has created conditions that make compliance with these requirements more difficult (lack of electricity, water and soil quality due to hostilities, etc.), but they remain important for protecting the rights and, above all, the health of consumers.

How children and adults were fed in the subway in the first months of the war (photo from open sources)

Facebook

Sergiy Zhuk

Director of the Charitable Organization "Charitable Foundation "Source of Revival" (CFSR)

CFSR activities

The food situation, especially in rural and remote areas, has become extremely acute due to the crisis and military events. Residents of villages and farms have found themselves cut off from civilization: the lack of electricity and suspended public transportation have made it difficult for them to survive.

On the measures taken to support the rural sector:

1. First, the problems of delivering food to residents who were and are in shelters and safe spaces were resolved.
2. Second, the basic conditions for cooking in a particular area have been created.
3. The next step was to provide food to city residents who were temporarily staying at metro stations during the shelling.
4. After the de-occupation of the Kharkiv region, efforts are being made to ensure its sustainable development. The Foundation, with the help of donors, provides assistance to rural areas for their restoration and development.
5. Private farms can provide themselves with food. This leads to the fact that they no longer need finished products (raw materials), but can produce them on their own on their farms. This contributes to an increase in jobs through self-employment.
6. Assistance in the development of the agricultural sector leads to job creation.

General information about humanitarian work in rural areas

“Before the war, we all heard about the Holodomor, and it was a topic that was very political. And apart from what our grandparents told us, we did not realize that this topic could become relevant at some point in time.”

The first days of the war were a test and a challenge for many of us. At this time, it was important to unite with other organizations and take care of the population that remained vulnerable. Although these challenges were difficult, a lot has been done over the past two years.

The main task was to create confidence in the future, that people would have access to food. Providing the population with this basic need has become extremely important. Rural communities and those remote from large cities suffered the most from food insecurity.

That is why, at present and since the first days of the full-scale war in Ukraine, the main focus of the Foundation's activities is charitable (humanitarian) assistance to the population suffering from the war in the combat zone and in the de-occupied territories of Kharkiv region.

Support for the medical industry in Kharkiv region (photo: Facebook by CFSR).

Facebook

Instagram

Kateryna Lavrenko

Manager of the Humanitarian Department of the Charitable Organization “Relief Coordination Center” and FSLC coordinator in Kharkiv region

Activities of the Charitable Organization “Relief Coordination Center” in the de-occupied territories

“The center appeared in September 2022 after the liberation of Kharkiv region. This happened with the support of the Eventroom Foundation – they evacuated people who lived near the Pechenizka Dam. When the Kharkiv region was de-occupied, many foundations immediately went to help large cities such as Vorzhansk, Kupiansk, Izyum, and Balakliia. At the same time, other settlements also needed help. That is why we created a humanitarian center in partnership with the Department of Civil Protection of the region and Kharkiv Regional Military Administration.”

CHC activities in Kharkiv region
(Photo by Relief Coordination Center)

Activities of the Charitable Organization “Relief Coordination Center”

The center aims to improve cooperation between local authorities and volunteer organizations in evacuating the population and providing humanitarian aid, including food, in the de-occupied territories of Kharkiv region.

A prerequisite for the creation of the unified Relief Coordination Center was close cooperation between charitable foundations, the Kharkiv Regional Military Administration and the Ministry of Reintegration of the Temporarily Occupied Territories of Ukraine.

The most successful example of such cooperation was the evacuation of the population through the Pecheneg Dam. More than 16 thousand people were evacuated.

Main goals of the organization:

1. Creating and maintaining a unified database of assistance requests by establishing sustainable links with local authorities, communities and their residents to maximize the satisfaction of immediate needs.
2. Planning and coordination of humanitarian and evacuation missions, taking into account the overall humanitarian situation in the region, avoiding duplication of assistance and expanding the coverage area.
3. Initiate cooperation between regional, national, and international organizations to achieve the most efficient allocation of resources and create new joint social projects.

Instagram

Yevhen Koliada

Head of the Charitable Organization
“Relief Coordination Center”

Activities of the Charitable Organization “Relief Coordination Center” in the de-occupied territories

“The center was created to avoid gaps in the provision of basic needs for the returned settlements.”

The RCC coordinates humanitarian missions of charitable foundations and organizations.

The main resource of the Relief Coordination Center is information. Every day, the team works to obtain up-to-date information and use it effectively in the future, to help philanthropists allocate their resources properly and avoid duplication of aid.

Every day, the RCC collects information about needs from local governments and seeks resources from foundations.

CHC’s activities during the war: food and construction materials (Photo by Relief Coordination Center)

Activities of the Charitable Organization “Relief Coordination Center”

What problems did the center solve and how?

Problem: The chaotic work of charitable organizations and benefactors leads to uneven distribution of humanitarian aid.

Solution: Constant communication between the RCC coordinators and representatives of local authorities and activists to update needs and requests. Representatives of the district and local authorities know what kind of humanitarian or evacuation mission the organizations are going on. Introduce statistics on the assistance provided and prepare an interactive map of requests.

Problem: 450+ organizations with varying access to humanitarian resources and, in addition, sporadic, self-organized volunteers and organizations still prevalent.

Solution: Involving more and more charitable organizations in cooperation. Demonstration of information of interest to organizations (people’s needs, contacts of other organizations, coordination with other local and international organizations).

CHC’s activities during the war: helping with clothing and basic necessities (Photo by Relief Coordination Center)

The Center has developed an interactive map of humanitarian aid. It displays the status of the settlement and the level of aid coverage.

This allows organizations to see up-to-date information and avoid duplication of aid when sending it to a settlement in need.

Svitlana Berezhna

Representative of
“Corus International”

“Restoring agricultural livelihoods to ensure food security in Ukraine”

Restoring livelihoods in agriculture to ensure food security in Kharkiv Region

“Corus International works with international and local networks to advance humanitarian efforts aimed at building capacity and resilience, while supporting Ukrainians in their own recovery initiatives.”

The purpose of the organization’s mission in the Kharkiv region is to promote the restoration of means of production, organic production and market relations for individuals engaged in personal farming (if they have agricultural land plots on the right of ownership or use) to ensure food security and social and economic sustainability of the communities of Kharkiv and Chuhuiv districts of Kharkiv region under martial law.

As part of the project, Corus International invited local residents and internally displaced persons (IDPs) involved in agricultural production/services in Kharkiv and Chuhuiv districts of Kharkiv region to join training sessions on growing on home gardens and provided borscht kits for growing.

After the de-occupation of the Kharkiv region, the organization provided more than 5,000 kits for growing food on small plots of land to increase the resilience of families in the de-occupied territories. Thus, households were able to provide themselves with vegetables on their own.

To help people grow regardless of the weather conditions, Corus International provided small greenhouses for people to install on their own land.

The organization also provided chickens for raising, with preliminary training to raise awareness and interest in their own production.

The next step in supporting and ensuring food security in communities was a microgrant competition aimed at developing small businesses. Microgrants will allow small agricultural businesses to develop and for many will be the start of producing their own local products.

*The first winners of the competition
(photo by CI representatives in Kharkiv region)*

Instagram

@CORUS.INTERNATIONAL

Anna Golovina

Representative of
“Zero Waste Kharkiv”

Activities of “Zero Waste Kharkiv”

**There is an eco-hub in Kharkiv,
which has five zones:**

1. **A reuse zone:** “People bring their things that they no longer want to use, but they are in good condition. Most of the things are taken by others, and the organization gives some of them as a charitable contribution, which is used to rent the eco-hub premises.”
2. **Circular construction and repair zone:** “Unused and used goods suitable for reuse that will be needed for repair and reconstruction: ceramic tiles, wallpaper, bricks, paint and paint residues, nails, mixtures, furniture, faucets, toilets, etc. The main area - CC Yard - is located in the village of Ruska Lozova in the Dergachiv community.”
3. **Deep sorting area:** “Today, you can already bring recyclable waste, because it is guaranteed to be taken by the eco-hub employees to procurers and enterprises for processing.”
4. **A repair and upcycling workshop:** “There is a craftswoman there who can repair things with minor damage, or you can bring fabric from which the craftswoman will sew a custom-made mask, shopper, eco-bags, etc. In particular, the hub sews poufs from used fabric that are filled with shredded metallized polypropylene packaging (which, at present, can only be shredded, not recycled).”
5. **“Zero Waste is a store”:** “A store of eco-friendly products that will replace disposable plastic items; everything that you can't just find in the supermarket: eco-mugs, bamboo ear buds, reusable diapers, bamboo toothbrushes, and many more useful things.”

Zero waste principles in practice “Zero Waste Kharkiv”

“The main goal of our main project, Circular Construction in Practice, is to help people rebuild their homes damaged by the hostilities in a circular way.”

Circular production (Ruska Lozova):

(photo by Zero Waste Kharkiv)

“The project started with waste sorting in Kharkiv. Now the project is being implemented in the city of Liubotyn. Liubotyn is the second city after Lviv to embark on the “zero waste” path. With the assistance of the organization, 10 composters have already been installed.”

CC Yard in Ruska Lozova village, where construction waste and items that are handed over to affected residents for housing reconstruction are accumulated (photo by Zero Waste Kharkiv)

Arrangement of the “Zero Waste Yard” center
(photo by Zero Waste Kharkiv)

This is the first pilot project in Ukraine on a circular approach to recovery, funded by Helvetas, the Swiss Solidarity Foundation, and SDC.

Facebook

Instagram

Tetiana Chernikova

Co-founder of NGO "Green Landia" and "Food for you"

Activities of the "Food for you"

"Food for You" is a family business specializing in the production of natural and environmentally friendly food. During its existence, it has been relocated twice.

The raw materials for the products are supplied by people living in the community in Poltava Region. This way, the company receives environmentally friendly products, and local residents receive additional income.

After production, the products are packaged and shipped to the hottest spots in Ukraine. Also, anyone can buy Food for You products on the organization's website or in the best stores in Ukraine.

One of the features of "Food for You" is that the company focuses on social impact and social responsibility indicators, namely:

1. 100% of the team consists of IDPs and people from other vulnerable categories;
2. 1078 units of products worth UAH 83 thousand were donated as charity;
3. 40 households have additional income from cooperation with "Food for You."

The production workshop of "Food for You" products
(photo from the official website of Green Landia)

Link to the project's Instagram

"Green Landia's" activities during the war: Challenges and opportunities

"We have a mission that keeps us working and moving forward. The mission is to provide people with natural, tasty food that promotes health and improves the quality of life (in all circumstances)."

Business model "Food for you"
(photo from Tetiana's presentation)

Наші переваги:

- АСОРТИМЕНТ**
40 страв традиційної української кухні
- СМАК**
Відомі перевірені рецепти, смак — як вдома
- НАТУРАЛЬНІСТЬ**
Тільки натуральні продукти без хімічних харчових добавок
- ЗРУЧНІСТЬ**
Страви готові до вживання. Вікрив і з'їв! Зберігаються без холодильнику протягом 2х років.
- ДОСТУПНІСТЬ**
Смачні страви може дозволити собі кожен

Benefits of the company
(photo from Tetiana's presentation)

Anna Titenko

Director of the Karazin Institute of Environmental Sciences

Project activities

“Compared to Karazin University, agrarian education has its own unique flavor, because we try to combine the competencies of a manager, an IT specialist, and someone who deals with decision-making in the field of agricultural management.”

Our project is:

1. Environmental education;
2. Environmental research;
3. Environmental services;
4. International projects.

“We are involved in various projects that are related to the problem that is being raised today regarding nutrition, the need to feed on the one hand, and to preserve the environment on the other.”

The project is actively involved in activities related to the safe use of land, including in the de-occupied territories and those affected by active hostilities in the region.

Безпека використання земель
Проблема та пріоритети

- >1,2 млн га заміновано в Харківській області (це 447 населених пунктів)
- Мінімум 150 років – на розмінування лише в Харківській області
- > 60 тис вибухів від влучань снарядів
- до 40% від загальної кількості - боєприпаси, що не вибухнули

Необхідність відновлення та використання земель

Modern agricultural management: ecological approaches and practical cases

“Our mission is to train those who can implement what no one else could.”

*Students of the Institute
(photo provided by the Institute of Ecology)*

“Our students are the ones who will implement many different environmental projects tomorrow, and we are confident that the revival of our country is their task.”

*Students of the Institute
(photo provided by the Institute of Ecology)*

Our plan is to create a sustainable international partnership to build a safe ecological system in the region.

Facebook

Instagram

Boiko Dmytro

Head of the Political Sociology Department, School of Sociology, Karazin University.

Stereotypes about healthy eating

2. The idea of «healthy eating»

Results of the survey on perceptions of a healthy lifestyle

“We are surprised that almost 25% of respondents grow food at home, i.e., they are engaged in urban farming, which is a significant figure for a Ukrainian metropolis. Particularly significant progress in this area occurred during wartime, as a significant number of people who stayed in the city began to arrange land plots near their entrances to grow herbs, vegetables, and berries.”

Assessment of food quality and waste sorting practices during the war: interim results of the study

“Among the trends, the following is interesting: it is significant that men’s diets have changed more than women’s. This can be explained by the fact that part of the family – women – were able to go abroad, and therefore their role in cooking and monitoring food processes in the family decreased. This is one of the factors of the war and martial law.”

1. Changes in diet quality

Research results: changes in diet quality

Another factor of the war’s impact on everyday nutrition is the following: the majority of people whose diets have changed are living in dormitories and are classified as IDPs. This category of people has seen a significant deterioration in their diet. The changes also affect the youngest and oldest groups of the population, i.e. those under 20 and those over 60. This is also partly explained by the military realities and the deteriorating economic situation.

3. Self-assessment of the «healthiness» of nutrition

Results of the survey on respondents’ self-assessment of healthy eating

Preliminary results of the study.

1. Noticeable deterioration in daily dietary intake, but relatively high level of satisfaction
2. Identification of risk groups: IDPs and men.
3. Vague and tautological understanding of the idea of “healthy eating.”
4. Lack of consistent and sustainable patterns of perception of healthy eating practices.
5. Understanding the limitations of information methods for promoting healthy eating and the need for a systematic approach to implementing healthy eating practices.

Link to the survey from the Fusilli project

Facebook of the project

Vil Bakirov

Doctor of Sociological Sciences, Academician of the National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine, President of the Sociological Association of Ukraine.

“The issue of food security and war is one of the systemic, painful, urgent and important problems that is only beginning to be felt and, unfortunately, will become more acute with each passing year.”

1. This is a complex problem that cannot be solved solely by the efforts of either the state or citizens alone. Everyone must work together in a comprehensive manner.
2. It is also important to establish a permanent, sustainable and flexible coordination and communication system that will facilitate and improve the process of interaction between different stakeholders.
3. There is no need to hush up this problem or ignore it, because it will get worse with each passing year and will have a variety of consequences for us.

“Solving the problems and issues that were discussed at the forum today is also a task for Ukrainian sociology to help establish interaction between different stakeholders; to join the development of new practices and policies for sustainable development and reconstruction of Ukraine.”

Official website of the Sociological Association of Ukraine

What are the prospects for further sociological research?

1. You can interview farmers who work directly in the de-occupied territories or in the territories affected by active hostilities.
2. It is also worth paying attention to retail chains, in particular in Kharkiv, how they worked in the first months of the war, how they changed their logistics, how they adapted to the new realities of work.
3. A survey of food producers, in particular in Kharkiv and the region, could also be interesting.
4. Another aspect is to study the changing behavior of consumers as key actors in food relations in the city.
5. It would also be interesting not just to research, but to build an interactive map or a sustainable “database” of people who have problems getting food and need specific assistance. These are not only those who belong to the so-called vulnerable groups, but also those who have found themselves in this situation because of the war.

“A new generation of specialists is now being educated, including at our Karazin University, so we need to ask them about their vision of our future, to involve them in solving issues not only of improving the environment but also of building a sustainable food security system.”

5R principles: definition and meaning

“When we started, the term “zero waste” was only used to describe production practices and waste management at the city level, it was not a term to describe a lifestyle. But when I saw the term, a light bulb went off in my head and I thought: «This is what we should be doing at home»” - Bea Johnson (from an interview with “The Rachelian Report”).

In 2008, French eco-activist Bea Johnson started working on individual environmental responsibility. A global problem is the constant increase in waste that affects the environment (or will in the near future), but this waste is not only the result of the activities of large or medium-sized enterprises, companies, etc. It is also the result of the activities of each individual or household. Bea Johnson's idea is that if each person minimizes the amount of their own waste, then the amount of waste will be minimized globally. She calls this approach a "zero waste" lifestyle. In 2013, she published the book *Zero Waste Home: The Ultimate Guide to Simplifying your Life by Reducing your Waste*, which has been translated into more than 20 languages. In the book, the author explains how every household can reduce waste. The method she invented is called the 5R principle. She outlined the principles in the form of a pyramid.

The pyramid reflects the principles from the most accessible to the most difficult to comply with. So, what does each principle mean:

1. **REFUSE**. It means refusing to consume excessively (buy only what you really need).
2. **REDUCE**. It means reducing the consumption and use of products (buy as much as you need).
3. **REUSE**. It means reusing products suitable for this purpose (reuse of plastic bottles, bags, for example).
4. **RECYCLE** - sorting and recycling, proper sorting is one of the first steps to being able to recycle some products into others, so everyone can make this process faster and more efficient.
5. **ROT** - composting. Recycling of organic waste.

The above principles have become a kind of roadmap for environmental awareness and help shape individual ecological behavior, but these principles are somewhat more difficult to implement in practice, depending on the cultural environment, one's own readiness to follow the principles, etc.

Therefore, an important element of implementation is not only knowledge of the principles but also the acquisition of practical skills and the habit of following them in different conditions.

*This article is a direct quote from a special issue of the interdisciplinary electronic collection of scientific papers on sociology and social work "SOCIOHPOCTIP": "FUSILLI: research through the prism of own experience during the war", pp. 61-66. The [full issue](#) is available here:

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